

Hard Density Fibreboards- Hardboards‘ enhanced circular use

Hardboards (i.e., high density fibre – HDF – boards) are panels that can't be made purely from recycled wood due to the necessity of fresh fibres needed for the wet processing technology for producing them. Hardboards can be used in almost all interior applications. When processing with wet technology, the lignin from fresh wood acts as a natural binder, which makes the boards non-toxic, recyclable and reusable. With no added resins, the formaldehyde content is the same as it is for natural wood. For this reason, this technology is a circularity enabler. The hardboards can be used for various indoor application fields including furniture components, wall panelling, moulded door skins, underlayment, perforated boards and others. This enables broader end life options and enhances resource efficiency of the overall production.

Image: nova-Institute

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Reduced use of chemicals since no resin is used
- ▶ The feature of the hardboards without synthetic resins enhances waste management options, reuse and recycling while reinforcing already eco-design
- ▶ Resource efficiency is improved by better cascading, reuse and recycling options
- ▶ The public is made aware about resin free alternatives, which teaches and increases understanding of circularity requirements
- ▶ The environmental footprint of the boards is optimised through reduced emissions
- ▶ Large potential for use in indoor applications where high emission standards are required

Regional coverage and transferability

Several companies that manufacture hardboards have been identified across Europe. Since the boards are used in so many applications, of which many are interior design, the target market is not dependent on the location of the production facility. It therefore can be said that the technology can be used and transferred widely.

